

Rotating Constants with the Best Next KBA Method

Most master keying software today supports rotating constants and as a result many people have only learned the “left to right” method usually taught in master key classes. In this article we will look at a method that goes back to at least the 1960s at Schlage Lock Co. We could call it the “Best Next Key Biting Array” method. It’s still useful in a number of situations, but its primary value is in showing the principles of managing key systems and key records over time.

We will start by considering a 6-pin master key system with two consonants that has used all of the changes shown in the key biting array (KBA) below. In this case that was 240 changes. There were 16 MACS violators that couldn’t be used. “MACS” means Maximum Adjacent Cut Specification. The MACS for Schlage is 7, so change keys like 235904 that have a difference of more than 7 in two adjacent positions can’t be used.

0	3	9	4	5	4
2	1	8	7		
4	3	2	1		
6	5	6	3		
8	7	0	9		

The analyst who set the system up decided to use two constants, and it looks like they opted to use them in positions to reduce MACS loss and to avoid master pins in the tip pin chamber.

The last pin chamber (Schlage is written bow to tip) is the most common place to have a master pin problem, and with a constant those problems are completely eliminated. There are other benefits too; a solid pin at the tip provides better protection from partially inserted keys, and it’s the hardest pin to reach with lockpicks. These good design decisions are not the kind of thing that require special notes or documentation in the records. When we go into the system to service the system, we find everything we need to know by looking at the KBA and the current list of bittings.

Now suppose we need another 50 change keys. The KBA is exhausted so we will rotate a constant and create a new one. We will only create one more KBA; we will not write out all 15 KBAs by rotating the constants thru every possible position. We don’t know what will happen to this system in the future: The customer could rekey, they could ask for cross keying or additional levels of keying. Writing out KBAs that may never be used would be a waste of time, and would make the records harder to read as well. Our goal is to provide the 50 changes that we need today, leave the system in good shape for the future, and document our work.

As noted earlier, the constant in the tip position has many benefits so we will try to keep it for as long as possible. That gives us four choices on where to place the other constant- the one that’s currently under the 3 in the TMK. Those four positions are the ones that are progressed in the KBA above. It’s worth taking a moment to look closely at that KBA and study the options. When you

look, consider that in practice you will likely never see this KBA again so don't get too used to it. Away from this example you will rotate constants in many different KBAs, the constants will be in different locations and the decisions on which constant to anchor may be based on other factors. What is always true is that the second KBA will have a constant in a position that is currently progressed, and it will have progression possibilities in a position that was held constant in the first KBA.

Even with experience, it takes some time to work through the four options. Many people use scratch paper, which is fine. The KBA is really a drawing, and you are analyzing one drawing and considering how to make a second drawing. Take your time and convince yourself that in this example our second KBA will progress the 3 in the Top Maser Key (TMK) and place the constant under either the 0, the 9, the 4 (in the fourth pin chamber) or the 5.

A constant under a 0 or 9 will result in a KBA with high MACS loss. If you pick these positions for constants and the system lasts a long time, someone in the future will have to create a third KBA sooner than necessary causing them to disparage your lack of foresight and poor master keying skills. Additionally making the 0 cut a constant would lose the benefit of the progressed shallow cut. A progressed shallow cut prevents change keys from being filed down to make the TMK. The 4 or the 5- pin chambers 4 and 5- are better choices for the second constant. We will take the 4.

That decision is probably made on scratch paper, so the next step will be to create actual documentation. We do that by drawing a new KBA, but in today's world we would enter the KBA, take a screenshot and paste it into the records.

The goal of the documentation is to make the next person's job easier. You don't want them to have to take in more information than necessary to understand what you did. For many of us, the documentation below is a good compromise:

	KBA1	KBA2
Hold Cut 6	0 3 9 4 5 4	0 3 9 4 5 4
	2 1 8 7	2 1 1 7
	4 3 2 1	4 5 3 1
	6 5 6 3	6 7 5 3
	8 7 0 9	8 9 7 9

Now with two KBAs complete, let's fast forward in time. Imagine that we've received many orders into the system and we look at the records from a point far in the future where we have completed our 5th KBA.

	KBA1	KBA2	KBA3	KBA4	KBA5
Hold Cut 6	0 3 9 4 5 4	0 3 9 4 5 4	0 3 9 4 5 4	0 3 9 4 5 4	0 3 9 4 5 4
	2 1 8 7	2 1 1 7	2 1 1 8	2 5 6 7	1 1 8 7
	4 3 2 1	4 5 3 1	4 5 3 2	4 7 8 1	5 3 2 1
	6 5 6 3	6 7 5 3	6 7 5 6	6 9 2 3	7 5 6 3
	8 7 0 9	8 9 7 9	8 9 7 0	8 9	7 0 9

These KBAs were not written all at once. They were created as needed, with the analyst writing the best KBA at that point in time. You can see the preference of writing out the KBA with as many changes as possible. Analysts follow that principle right up to a point.

KBA4 is a short KBA; the solid 9 wipes out progression possibilities in the neighboring positions. Someone selected it before writing out KBA5 because using KBA5 will require either manually eliminating changes that can be cut down to make the TMK, or accepting the risk of using a key like 017234 as a change key. Many organizations find the risk from using a small number of these changes negligible, but whoever wrote KBA 4 opted to move that decision into the future. In general, you don't want to make a decision that takes something away from a key system until it's necessary.

KBA5 marks a new point in the lifecycle of the system. Until now, we have a constant that had not been rotated. There are two things we can do with constants: rotate them to get more changes, or create systemwide selective keys: 039450, 039452, 039456, and 039458. Using these keys in a 2-level system is rare but it costs us nothing to preserve the capability and we try to keep it for as long as possible. In the unlikely event that the system requires cross keying or additional levels of keying in the future, someone- maybe our future selves- will thank us for leaving that constant intact for as long as possible.

We'll take another step forward in time to consider what the records will look like as we add KBA6 through KBA9. Here's the system after around 1,800 more changes:

	KBA1	KBA2	KBA3	KBA4	KBA5	
Hold Cut 6	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 1 8 7 4 3 2 1 6 5 6 3 8 7 0 9	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 1 1 7 4 5 3 1 6 7 5 3 8 9 7 9	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 1 1 8 4 5 3 2 6 7 5 6 8 9 7 0	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 5 6 7 4 7 8 1 6 9 2 3 8 9	0 3 9 4 5 4 1 1 8 7 5 3 2 1 7 5 6 3 7 0 9	
	KBA6	KBA7	KBA8	KBA9		
	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 1 8 8 4 3 2 2 6 5 6 6 8 7 0 0	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 1 7 8 4 3 1 2 6 5 3 6 8 7 9 0	0 3 9 4 5 4 2 8 7 8 4 2 1 2 6 6 3 6 8 9 0	0 3 9 4 5 4 1 8 7 8 3 2 1 2 5 6 3 6 7 0 9 0		
	Hold Cut 2					

In KBAs after 5, the four cut in the tip position will be highlighted in red to indicate that it's off limits for use as a constant. When we create KBA10 in a moment we will highlight both the tip position and the 3 in the second pin chamber in red for the same reason.

To be historically accurate, at Schlage we did not specifically write down the anchor constant in the records and we didn't highlight the exhausted position in red. We just wrote down the next KBA. We also didn't write down "KBA1 next to the first KBA since this was obvious, and we did write in the SOP, omitted here to save space and make the graphics easier to follow.

The master key analysts of that era handled around 200 different systems a month with either no software or software that could only create 64 bitting at a time. They read and wrote KBAs for a living. We don't do that anymore. In this era we let the software rotate constants and the patterns of KBA development are less obvious to us. Every shop needs to decide on their own level of documentation, but for most I recommend a method that provides more guidance than the way we wrote things back in the 1980s and 90s at Schlage.

Documenting the way shown here also reveals a pattern that occurs with two rotating constants that will help you count the number of KBAs. In a 6-pin cylinder with 2 constants we get $5+4+3+2+1 = 15$ KBAs. If we selected two constants in 7-pin cylinders we would get $6+5+4+3+2+1=20$ KBAs. If we are rotating 2 constants thru four pin chambers (and this is fairly common because we use it to create KBAs with parity changes) you will get $3+2+1=6$ KBAs. Write some out yourself and you will see the pattern clearly.

Now let's fast forward again on our system. The record below shows the system entering old age, with all 15 KBAs use.

	KBA1	KBA2	KBA3	KBA4	KBA5
Hold Cut 6	039454 2 187 4 321 6 563 8 709	039454 2 117 4 453 6 753 8 897	039454 2 118 4 453 6 756 8 897	039454 2 567 4 781 6 923 8 9	039454 2 1187 4 5321 6 7563 8 709
Hold Cut 2	039454 2 18 8 4 32 2 6 56 6 8 70 0	039454 2 1 78 4 3 12 6 5 36 8 7 90	039454 2 878 4 212 6 636 8 90	039454 2 1878 4 3212 6 5636 8 7090	
Hold Cut 4	039454 2 11 8 4 53 2 6 75 6 8 897 0	039454 2 5 18 4 7 32 6 9 76 8 8 90	039454 2 11 18 4 53 32 6 75 76 8 7 90		
Hold Cut 5	039454 2 1 8 8 4 5 2 2 6 7 6 6 8 0 0	039454 2 1 18 8 4 5 32 2 6 7 56 6 8 7 0 0			
Hold Cuts 1 & 3	039454 2 5 878 4 7 212 6 636 8 90				

Today, we prefer to let the software rotate constants. With many programs you can sort and rename bittings to get all of the features we got using the "best next KBA" method, and you can do even better by randomizing change key assignment. The principles demonstrated by this old-school method are still valid though, and apply to pretty much all master key systems:

1. At every step, leave as many options for the future as possible.
2. Create documentation that's complete and concise. The person who works behind you should not have to read a novel to figure out what you did, and they shouldn't have to take time to reverse-engineer because of your failure to document.
3. Don't do unnecessary work on a system that may not be needed, but don't omit planning. Planning is not unnecessary work. Plan so that you leave the records, as well as the system, in the best possible shape for the next person.

Readers working with access control systems will find these guidelines apply in their world as well.

Thanks for reading-

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